

Information Resources for Visually Impaired Student for Effective Service Delivery in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria

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Abstract

Keywords:
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Introduction: This study investigated the information resources available for visually impaired students to ensure effective service delivery at Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) library, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The study aimed to determine the necessary information resources for visually impaired students, identify sources for providing these resources, explore challenges associated with their provision, and find strategies for enhancing resource availability for visually impaired students at ABU, Zaria.

Methodology: A descriptive survey research design was employed. The study population comprised 90 students and librarians from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Data collection instruments included interviews and questionnaires. Two research assistants, briefed on the study objectives, helped administer and retrieve the instruments within two weeks. Data were analyzed using percentages, means, and standard deviations to answer the research questions.

Findings/Results: The study revealed that university libraries should utilize specialized software and hardware designed to aid visually impaired students in accessing printed materials. These tools include screen readers, text-to-speech software, and braille displays, which ensure equal access to resources. The study also identified the challenges faced in providing these resources and the need for effective strategies to overcome them.

Conclusion: The study concluded that while specialized information resources are essential for visually impaired students at ABU, Zaria, there are significant challenges in their provision. Addressing these challenges is crucial for ensuring effective service delivery and equal access to resources for visually impaired students.

Recommendations: The study recommended that university libraries should implement and maintain specialized software and hardware for visually impaired students. This includes investing in screen readers, text-to-speech software, and braille displays. Additionally, libraries should develop strategies to overcome challenges in resource provision, ensuring that visually impaired students have equal access to all necessary information resources.

Introduction

Visually impaired are people who require the use of special means to perceive what people normally and naturally see (Osinuga, Akolade *et al.*, 2015). Visually impaired persons are considered as part of persons with disabilities. Information materials for the visually impaired must be transcribed into alternative format before they are made available for use. A person with visual impairments mostly depends on information sources available in large print, audio books, talking books, and braille materials (Adetoro, & Atinmo, 2012). The mere fact that some students cannot walk freely about should not prevent them from utilizing library resources that are provided for their able-bodied visually impaired can be described as persons who cannot read standard print with remedial lenses (Onoyeyan, 2019). In their view, Mandal (2015) defined visually impaired as a term used to describe people that have partial sight or complete blindness. Whereas Aghauche & Udem, (2018) see visually impaired as persons who are blind or have a low vision. In most cases visually impaired persons term is applied to both people who suffer from total as well as partial blindness. World Health Organization (2013) estimated that about 285 million people are estimated to be visually impaired worldwide, 39 million are blind and 246 have low vision. About 99% of the visually impaired live in low income setting while 82% of people living with blindness are age 50 and above. Furthermore, Adetoro (2011) established that Federal Ministry of Health as cited by the Lagos state branch of the Nigerian Optometric Association (NOA) shows that people with blindness are over one million with about three million others with visual impairment, they posited that 42 out of every 100 adult people above the age of 40 are visually impaired in Nigeria. This means that the visually impaired persons in Nigeria are on the increase and care has to be taken to reduce the number.

Information requirements just like those without disability (Akolade *et al.*, 2015). The need of fully able body people without disability might read textbooks, watch documentaries, listen to audio documents or download electronic information from the Internet, so also visually impaired people want access to relevant information in their chosen accessible format. As additional persons with disabilities attend higher institutions, it is mandatory upon library stakeholders to provide the required resources and information to them just like how it is done to the normal users. It is no more a doubt, that this category of students are making use of libraries and requires enhanced assistance in their search for the numerous information they need to survive academic challenges and beyond. A vital obligation for libraries is the information they preserve and deliver in many formats must be made available to all including physically challenged users (Atinmo, 2000).

Information resources sharing refer to the method whereby libraries with common interest pool their materials together in order to meet their users' needs much more than they could have done on individual effort. Babalola, & Yacob, (2011) defined resource sharing as the activities that result from an agreement, formal or informal, among a group of libraries (usually a consortium or network) to share collections, data, facilities, personnel, etc., for the benefit of their users and to reduce the expense of collection development. According to Friend (2009) many new approaches on resource sharing are now emerging worldwide which include the use of the Internet for accessing millions of bits of information all over the globe. The electronic mail, teleconferencing and video conferencing are typical examples. A networking model can be local, regional, national or international. Its main purpose is for the electronic transfer of information between two or more libraries. Imperatively, there is need for special education center libraries to share and provide

its information resources among partner libraries if they must ensure effective teaching of physically challenged pupils. The objective of resource sharing among special education center libraries is to provide convenient access to information to the physically challenged pupils for effective learning. Some of the notable methods of resource sharing among special education center libraries are inter library loan and co-operative cataloguing, co-operative storage and reference, reprographic service, documentation center, union list of serials and bibliographies.

Library service is the professional guidance and assistance offered to the users which varies in accordance with the types or categories of library users. According to Eguavoen, & Eniola, (2007) services are the activities performed in an organized environment in the interest or for the benefit of another. The nature of services in any university libraries varies from one university to another because of different natures of research, curriculum activities and local needs of their users. When adequate services are provided, it leads to effective service delivery to the users. Kumar (2012) refers to services delivery as the provision of information on request which show that the user who demanded the information will be provided with answer to users query. Information provision can be in anticipation with the hope of keeping the users well informed in their field of specialization and up-to-date in their subject area.

This is reflected in the Special Education Unit of the revised National Policy on Education (2014) where provision is made for special education. Akolade *et al* (2015) reported that physically challenged people have the same information needs as people without disability. Like any other persons without disability, disabled students need to read newspaper, listen to a CD or download electronic information from the Internet to suit their

information needs. Despite the fact that academic libraries put their effort to satisfy the needs of their users, they however still neglect some group of users (physically challenged) in the information and service provision. In some, they tend to discriminate the disabled and shy them away from utilizing the library resources.

Effective service delivery can be seen as an essential goal of the performance management matrix that compares plan with the actual status, indicating deviation (if any), re-planning or corrective actions might result. It is a systematic effort by management to compare with plans. It can also be maintained for a relatively long period if organizations take necessary procedures to avoid performance setback (Anyim, 2020). To contextualize the above statement; effective service delivery is an appraisal of how a particular task is being achieved by the performer which in this context represents the librarians like the teacher librarians and every other person that has a stake in the promotion of education for the visually challenged students.

Objective of the Study

The main objectives of the study are to determine:

1. The information resources required for visually impaired students in A B U, Zaria, Nigeria.
2. The sources of providing information resources for visually impaired students in A B U, Zaria Nigeria
3. The challenges associated with information resources provision for visually impaired students in A B U, Zaria, Nigeria.
4. The Strategies for enhancing information resources provision for visually impaired student in A B U, Zaria, Nigeria.

Literature Review

The Copyright (Visually Impaired Persons) Act 2002, broadly defined a visually impaired person (VIP) as someone who is blind, partially sighted and whose eyesight cannot be improved by corrective lenses to allow them to read without a special level or kind of light, who is unable to either hold or manipulate a book or move the eyes to be able to read easily. In other words, any person who is not able to read in a conventional way is visually impaired. Visually impaired is a functional loss of vision than eye disorder. Eye disorders that can lead to visually impaired includes retinal degeneration, albinism, cataracts, and glaucoma, muscular problems that result in the visual disturbance, corneal disorders, diabetic retinopathy, congenital disorders and infection. Visually impaired affects how a child understands and functions in the world. It can affect a child's cognitive, emotional, neurological and physical development by limiting the range of experiences and kinds of information a child is exposed to.

Visually impaired as pointed out by Decarlo, Woo and Woo (cited in Naipal and Rampersad, 2018) is a condition of reduced visually performance that cannot be remedied by refractive correction (spectacles or contact lenses) in surgery, or medical methods. Accordingly, it results in functional limitations of the visual system that may be characterized by irreversible vision loss, restricted visual field and decreased contrast sensitivity, increased sensitivity to glare as decreased ability to perform activities of daily living, such as reading or writing (Kavitha, Manumali, Praveen, & Heralgi, 2015). This is why Eguavoen and Eniola (2007) noted that a young child with visual impairment has little reason to explore interesting objects in the environment and thus may miss opportunities to have experiences and learn and that this lack of exploration may continue until intervention.

Visually impaired has been classified into categories. Mbagwu, (2006) asserted that there are three categories of visual handicap which include total blindness, low vision and partial sightedness. Meanwhile, WHO identified three levels of visual capacity as normal vision, low vision and blindness. Low vision and blindness may result from three medical conditions that include reduced visual acuity, restricted field of vision and imperfect color vision. People with low vision can read large print materials, but those who are blind cannot read anything in print. Of the three types of visual impairment, blindness is the most common. Abosi and Ozoji (2011) asserted that a person is considered blind if he cannot read and write print after all optical corrective measures Incidence of visual challenged is on the increase. WHO in 2010 reported that there were 39 million blind people and 246 million people with moderate and severe vision impairment globally. In Nigeria, Mbagwu (2006) estimated that one out of every four school children had some visually problems.

Visually impaired students have same information requirements just like those without disability (Akolade et al., 2015). The need of fully able body people without disability might read textbooks, watch documentaries, listen to audio documents or download electronic information from the Internet, so also visually impaired people want access to relevant information in their chosen accessible format. As additional persons with disabilities attend higher institutions, it is mandatory upon library stakeholders to provide the required resources and information to them just like how it is done to the normal users. It is no more a doubt, that this category of students are making use of libraries and require enhanced assistance in their search for the numerous information they need to survive academic challenges and beyond. A vital obligation for libraries is the information they preserve and deliver in many formats must be

made available to all including physically challenged users (Wolffsohn, 2007).

Zia & Fatima (2011) lamented that libraries provide access to important resources and services that societies need to partake in the emerging information culture. In lieu of that, they have a moral obligation to provide same resources and services to all categories of users regardless of their gender, age, race, political affiliation or disability. It is from that inclusive, non-discriminatory service these libraries especially academic ones can help in creating awareness and stand by the official institute policy towards physically challenged students, providing a tailored, well-structured buildings as well as the whole educational programs that can accommodate all forms of disabilities and providing adequate information resources to them. These information provided for the disabled students must be capable of supporting research activities among students and faculty members. These students could be the visually impaired or normal library users. The visually impaired students will need assistance while in the library but the normal students may need little or no assistance. There is a wide range of information need by people with disability (especially those in academic institutions) in order for them to have access to information in a variety of formats and be able to use this knowledge to form their own opinions and participate in the development of a society. It has been librarians dream to offer everybody regardless of background and nationality access to the world's knowledge and wisdom. Ayiah (2007) lamented that there are a number of library and information facilities available to meet the library and information needs of persons with disability in tertiary institutions. These facilities are intended to simplify access to information and library with the hope that the information acquired will improve lives and help achieve their potentials. Ruth (2015) mentioned that, if truly there is ability in disability then library as overseers of

information exclusively academic libraries in Nigeria need to recognize these category of potential users and guarantee suitable policy and facilities that will assist them in meeting their information needs. The right time for a policy is now, Nigerian academic environment need to affirm its commitment to library information service for all including people with disabilities and then act accordingly.

Lawal-Solarin (2012) enumerated the following as the information needs of the physically challenged: (i) Information for educational development which is of paramount importance as a student, additional information would be needed to build on what was taught in the classroom; (2) information for social and personal development on assistive devices that could aid mobility and (iii) information for recreational purposes which may include materials for light reading. Therefore Information resources sharing refer to the method whereby libraries with common interest pool their materials together in order to meet their users' needs much more than they could have done on individual effort.

Kumar, (2012) refers to services delivery as the provision of information on request which show that the user who demanded the information will be provided with answer to users query. Information provision can be in anticipation with the hope of keeping the users well informed in their field of specialization and up-to-date in their subject area. Effective service delivery can be seen as an essential goal of the performance management matrix that compares plan with the actual status, indicating deviation (if any), re-planning or corrective actions might result. It is a systematic effort by management to compare with plans. It can also be maintained for a relatively long period if organizations take necessary procedures to avoid performance setback (Anyim, 2020).

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. Descriptive survey design according to Ngorgu (2015) aims at studying a group of people or items by collecting data from a sample of the same group or items considered appropriate to be a representative of the entire population. This design was appropriate for the study because it sought information from respondents on information resources for visually impaired student for effective service delivery in A B U, Zaria, Nigeria. The population of the study was 90 students all of which was because it was manageable. Total enumeration can be adopted when population

size is small and shares a common characteristic (Ibrahim 2013). The instruments used for data collection was structured questionnaires and interview. The research instrument was validated by two experts in the Department of library and information science and one from measurement and evaluation all from faculty of education Federal University Gashua. The data collected were analyzed using statistical package for social science to calculate mean and standard deviation.

Table: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on Information Resources Required For Visually impaired students in A B U, Zaria

SN	Information Resources	HE	M	LR	RR	N	Mean	STD	Decision
1	Braille Book	27	26	17	20	90	3.05	0.75	Accepted
2	Craft book	25	23	22	20	90	3.03	0.12	Accepted
3	Cassette Recorder	14	18	18	40	90	2.27	0.08	Rejected
4	Talking calculator	41	19	17	13	90	2.67	0.19	Accepted
5	Abacus, Mayplug slates, pencil guide	26	27	16	21	90	2.56	0.14	Accepted
6	Braille printer	29	24	16	21	90	2.90	0.10	Accepted
7	ICT/internet facilities	17	16	17	40	90	2.43	0.03	Rejected
8	E-book	33	25	15	17	90	3.01	0.31	Accepted
9	Book scanner with software	18	15	17	40	90	2.39	0.11	Rejected
10	CCTV magnifying Aid Unit	18	14	18	40	90	2.45	0.08	Rejected
11	Kuzeweil Reader	18	13	19	40	90	2.15	0.13	Rejected
12	Large print Books	30	28	15	17	90	2.86	0.02	Accepted
13	Talking Books	21	10	24	35	90	2.48	0.10	Rejected
14	Moon Books	21	10	15	44	90	1.95	0.15	Rejected
15	Audio Descriptive Video	30	27	16	17	90	3.00	0.86	Accepted
16	Tactile or Raised surface	22	9	14	45	90	2.36	0.96	Rejected
17	Audio Tape	33	25	14	18	90	2.79	0.08	Accepted
18	Twin Vision Books	21	10	14	45	90	2.21	0.98	Rejected
19	Screen magnifying monitor	34	24	14	18	90	2.56	0.11	Accepted

20	Computer with voice transmitter	21	10	15	44	90	2.40	0.12	Rejected
21	Journal/ Newspaper (in Braille)	35	23	14	18	90	2.73	0.15	Accepted
22	e-story books	33	23	15	19	90	2.54	0.09	Accepted
23	e-text book	30	24	14	19	90	3.00	0.26	Accepted
	Grand mean						2.58	0.29	

Key: High Resource (HR), Moderate Resources (MR), Low Resource (LR)

Table 1, it shows that visually impaired students mostly use braille book as their main information resources for study in the center. the finding showed that there are , three information properties that have higher score (Braille book, Graft book and e-text book), Braille book is ranked 1st with a mean score of 3.05 followed by Graft book with 3.03 and e-book 3. 01 in the special center

From the interview conducted, the respondents interviewed revealed that blind students mostly use Braille book, Graft book and e-text book for retrieving information. Specifically, it was affirmed by Mr. Gambo who was the librarian and informed that the students make use of braille book, Graft book for thier academic purposes. He attributed this to the fact that the students are more familiar with those than were listed in the study.

Table: 2 Mean And Standard Deviation of Respondents on what are the Sources of Provision of Information Resources for Visually Impaired Student in A B U, Zaria

SN	Sources of Provision of Information Resources	SA	A	DA	SD	N	Mean	STD	Decision
1	Purchase	12	13	22	43	90	2.42	0.94	Rejected
2	Donation from NGOs	44	23	15	13	90	3.00	0.03	Accepted
3	Government such as SUBEB,UBEC	30	25	15	20	90	2.55	0.19	Accepted
4	Gifts from PTA, individuals	35	25	20	10	90	2.57	0.12	Accepted
5	Sharing or exchange from other schools	13	20	27	30	90	2.35	0.15	Rejected
	Grand mean						2.57	0.29	

Key: SA =Strongly Agree; A= Agree; D=Disagree

Table 2 shows that responses to Donation from NGOs ranked first in the institutions with 3.00, in blind center followed by Gifts from PTA, individuals with 2.57, and This is followed by sharing and exchange from other schools (Government such as SUBEB,UBEC) all having their mean above 2.5.

This agrees with the response given during the interview sessions when the question was asked. The three respondents confirmed they use purchase, donations from NGO, Sharing or exchange from other center. This same report was also given by the other respondents from the library. However they expressed their joy in getting to know the main sources for provision of information.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondent on the Challenges Associated With Information Resources For Visually Impaired Students In A B U, Zaria

SN		SA	A	D	SD	N	Mean	STD	Decision
1	Insufficient funding	30	25	20	15	90	2.57	0.97	Accepted
2	Shortage of specialized personnel	33	22	20	15	90	2.69	0.63	Accepted
3	Inadequate provision of internet services	31	24	18	17	90	2.71	0.72	Accepted
4	Dearth of information resources	20	15	15	40	90	2.28	0.68	Rejected
5	Unstable power supply	32	23	19	16	90	2.55	0.56	Accepted
	Grand mean						2.56	0.71	

Key: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 3 shows that students accepted almost all the items as the challenges associated with information resources as their mean were above the criterion mean score of 2.5 except items 4 (Death of information resources).

This finding is in line with Uzoamaka et al (2002) that high cost of internet subscription and slow internet connectivity as being the

major challenges he experiences in the utilization and the use of internet information properties. There are too much irrelevant information before locating and retrieving of the desired information and even when the desired information has been found, there seems to be some restrictions in accessing them which is either from the authors or publisher.

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation Of Strategies For Enhancing Information Resources For Visually Impaired Students In A B U, Zaria

SN		SA	A	D	SD	N	Mean	STD	Decision
1	Provision of adequate funding to the school	20	20	17	33	90	2.41	0.55	Rejected
2	Provision of adequate specialized personnel	30	27	13	20	90	2.71	0.66	Accepted
3	Provision of adequate internet services to the school	19	18	19	34	90	2.45	0.25	Rejected
4	There is need for the availability of information resources to the visually challenged students	33	20	17	20	90	2.55	0.77	Accepted
5	Provision of adequate ICT infrastructure to the centre	20	20	16	34	90	2.37	0.13	Rejected
6	Proper welfare to the visually challenged in school	30	28	12	20	90	2.64	0.89	Accepted
7	Proper library orientation on how to use those information	34	19	18	19	90	2.77	0.78	Accepted

	available in those special education center libraries.								
8	There is need for constant power supply in the School	35	19	17	19	90	2.50	0.71	Accepted
	Grand mean						2.55	0.59	

Key: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 4 shows that provision of adequate personnel, Proper welfare to the visually impaired student, availability of information resources to the visually challenged students, Proper library orientation on how to use those information available in those special education center libraries, There is need for constant power supply in the School as their mean were above the criterion mean score of 2.5.

Conclusion

In conclusion, providing effective information resources for visually impaired students in university libraries requires a multi-faceted approach that integrates technology, specialized services, inclusive collection development, training programs, and collaborative efforts. By leveraging accessibility technologies such as screen readers and text-to-speech software, libraries can ensure that visually impaired students can access printed materials. Additionally, offering dedicated support services staffed by knowledgeable personnel can further enhance the student experience. Developing collections in alternative formats like braille, audio, and large print contributes to a more inclusive environment. Education and training programs help visually impaired students navigate library resources and assistive technologies effectively. Collaboration with disability services offices, student groups, and other stakeholders is crucial for advocacy and ongoing improvement of services. By adopting these strategies and fostering a culture of inclusivity, university libraries can deliver effective information resources to visually

impaired students, empowering them in their academic pursuits and fostering a more equitable learning environment.

Recommendations

1. Provision of alternative sources of power to combat the problem of erratic power supply and equipment's that are energy saving for longevity of use.
2. Provision of a specialized personnel librarian that is a well-equipped resource person in Visual impaired resources and services so as to impact in the skills that are needed to effectively utilize available information resources for visual impaired and researchers.
3. Acquisition of relevant information resources and proper welfare for the visually impaired students in the university
4. Regular Orientation to guide the visually impaired students on how to use the resources and access to the library Service.

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